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GEOMETRIK MASALALARNI BAJARISHNING ENG QULAY ALGORITMLARI

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Annotatsiya: This article is about the efficiency of using algorithm & the ways of solving them with positional tasks.

Kalit so‘zlar: undergraduate, triangle-shaped, adjacent, drawn, respect, Frontal, Remember.

Drawing geometry is taught to enhance the imagination of students of higher educational institutions, [4]. It is very convenient to use algorithms, noting that the level of imagination of undergraduate students in the field of Engineering, Architecture and design is insufficient, [3].

It is known that the projections H and V of an arbitrary triangle-shaped plane (Figure 1) Find the angular magnitudes of deviation with respect to the planes are solved by performing the following graphical operations, [1]:

A horizontal line $h(H'h'')$ is drawn through the C(C',C'') end of the triangular ABC (Figure 2).

draw 2

In the frontal projection of the Epirus, the frontal projection of the horizontal $h''(C''1'')$ is plotted through the C'' end of Triangle $a''B''c''$ parallel to the $[ox)$ axis. Then the missing horizontal projection of Point 1' is determined. This 1' point $a'B'C'$ lies on the $A'B'$ side of the Triangle. The C' and 1' points are adjacent. This line is denoted by h' and is called the horizontal projection of the horizontal,[5].

$$C'' \subset h''(C''1'') \parallel [ox) \text{ and } C' \in h'(C'1')$$

ABC is drawn through the B-end of the triangle with the line $m(m',m'')$ perpendicular to the line $h(h',h'')$ (Figure 3). This line $m(m',m'')$ is called the largest slope line of triangle ABC. lines $m(m',m'')$ and $h(h',h'')$ intersect to form a $D(D',D'')$ point. The result is a $[BD]$ cross section.

draw 3

In the horizontal projection of the Epirus, $a'B'C'$

is drawn through the B' end of the Triangle, drawing the M'line perpendicular to the $H'(C'1')$ line. the lines m' and h' intersect to form a D' point. And the D'' point lies

on the line $h''(C''1'')$. A line m is drawn through points B'' and D'' .

$$B' \subset m' \perp h'(C'1'); m' \cap h' = D'$$

$D'' \in h''(C''1'')$ and

$$B'' \cup D'' = [B''D''] \in m''$$

The actual length of the $[BD]$ cross section is determined using the right-angled triangle method. (Figure 4).

This results in a dbb_0 right-angled triangle.

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Its angle D is $\angle\alpha$, which is the angle of inclination to H.

That is, $\angle\alpha = (ABC) \wedge H$.

In the horizontal projection of the Epirus, the cross – section $[B'D']$ is equal to the 1st cathet of the right triangle. A cross section $B'B_0$ is drawn through the point $\Delta Z = (ZD - ZB)$ equal to the distance length and perpendicular to $B'D$. This incision forms cathet 2.

$$|B'B_0| = \Delta Z = Z_D - Z_B \text{ va}$$

$$|B'B_0| \perp [B'D]$$

Points B_0 and D' are adjacent. This $[B_0D']$ cross section forms the hypotenuse of the $D'B'B_0$ right triangle. Its D' end is $\angle\alpha$. I.e. $\angle\alpha = (ABC) \wedge H$

Answer. $D' = (ABC) \wedge H$

U Through the $C(C', C'')$ end of the triangular ABC the frontal line $f(f', f'')$ is plotted (Figure 5).

In the horizontal projection of the Epirus, a horizontal projection of the $F'(C'2')$ Frontal is drawn parallel to the $[ox]$ axis through the C' point. Then, the missing projection of Point $2''$ is determined. This point lies in $A''B''$. Points C'' and $2''$ are adjacent. This

line is denoted by f'' and is called the frontal projection of the frontal.

$$C' \subset f' \wedge (C' \wedge 1') \parallel [ox]; C'' \subset f'' \wedge (C'' \wedge 1'')$$

ABC is drawn through the A-end of the triangle with the line $n(n', n'')$ perpendicular to the line $f(f', f'')$ (Figure 6). This line $n(n', n'')$ is the kata-most oblique line of the ABC triangle, and defines the Triangle by defining the angle of deviation V to β

β . the lines $n(n', n'')$ and $f(f', f'')$ intersect to form the point $E(E', E'')$. This results in a cross section $[AE]$.

$$A \subset n(n', n'') \perp f(f', f''), n(n', n'') \in ABC$$

$$n(n', n'') \cap f(f', f'') = E(E', E''), [AE] \in m$$

In the frontal projection of the Epirus, a $B''C''$ is drawn through the A'' end of the Triangle n'' perpendicular to the line $f(f', f'')$.

$$A'' \subset n'' \perp f''(C''C')$$

the lines n'' and $f''(C'', C')$ intersect to form Point E'' .

$$n'' \cap f'' = E'' \langle Br \rangle$$

In the horizontal projection, the e 'point $F'(C', 2')$ belongs to the line.

$$E' \in f'(C'2')$$

The points A' and E' are contiguous and marked n' .

$$A' \cup E' = [A'E'] \in n'$$

The actual length of the $[Ae]$ Cross is determined using the right-angled triangle method (Figure 7). This results in an ea_0 right-angled triangle. Its angle E is $\angle\beta$, which is the angle of inclination to V . That is, $\angle\beta = (ABC) \wedge V$.

In the frontal projection of the Epirus, the cross – section $[A''E'']$ is equal to the 1st cathet of the right triangle. Through a point $\Delta Y = (Y_C - Y_A)$ a cross section $a''A_0$ is drawn, which is equal to the distance length and perpendicular to $A''E''$. Kes $a''A_0$ cross section forms cathet 2.

$$|A''A_0| = \Delta Y = Y_C - Y_A \text{ va } |A''A_0| \perp [A''E'']$$

Points A_0 and E'' are adjacent. This $/a_0e''/$ Cross $E''A''$ forms the hypotenuse of the A_0 right triangle. Its E'' TIP is $\angle\beta$.

Viz $\angle\beta = (ABC) \wedge V$

Answer: $\angle E'' = \angle\beta = (ABC) \wedge V$

Thus, when solving positional problems of this kind, drawing up a plan-algorithm using symbols, it becomes very easy to solve the problem as well as Remember the student. This increases student empowerment efficiency .

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